

Glossary of Gastrointestinal Disease Terms (English–Arabic)

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Introduction

The gastrointestinal (GI) system plays a crucial role in maintaining overall human health by facilitating digestion, nutrient absorption, immune defense, and waste elimination. Any disruption in its function can compromise multiple bodily systems, leading to a wide spectrum of health complications ranging from mild indigestion and functional disorders to chronic inflammatory diseases and severe, life-threatening conditions. In recent decades, the global burden of GI diseases has become increasingly evident, with research showing steady rises in prevalence linked to lifestyle factors, environmental changes, and improved diagnostic practices.

Epidemiological studies underscore the scale of this burden. Peery et al. (2019) demonstrated that gastrointestinal disorders remain among the principal causes of morbidity, healthcare utilization, and hospitalization in the United States, noting that acute pancreatitis continues to be one of the most frequent causes of emergency admissions. On a broader international level, Scallan et al. (2005) reported that acute gastrointestinal illness may occur as frequently as 3.5 episodes per person per year in developed countries, illustrating the pervasive nature of these conditions across diverse populations. Additional global health reports highlight similar trends in other regions, emphasizing that GI diseases not only affect quality of life but also create substantial economic and healthcare pressures.

Understanding gastrointestinal terminology is crucial due to its prevalence and complexity, as it enables effective communication in healthcare, education, and translation. Medical terminology forms the foundation for precise scientific communication, enabling specialists to accurately describe symptoms, diagnoses, and treatments. In gastroenterology, as in medical fields more broadly, effective management of terminology is essential for maintaining consistency and ensuring the accuracy of conveyed information.

However, translating medical terminology related to the gastrointestinal (GI) system presents numerous challenges that extend beyond mere literal lexical rendering. A significant problem in translating similar words is that their counterparts in the target language may also be similar. Furthermore, there may not be an equivalent phrase in the target language, further complicating the search for a substitute word. Additionally, a single term can have multiple meanings depending on its anatomical or clinical context, requiring the translator to understand each context to grasp the intended meaning. Moreover, given the rapid evolution of the medical field, medical translation necessitates continuous monitoring of advancements in medicine, drugs, and treatments to ensure accurate and up-to-date translations. These factors make terminology management a demanding task requiring meticulous research and the ongoing use of reliable medical references to maintain clarity and precision.

This glossary was developed to address these challenges by collecting, defining, and translating key terms related to gastrointestinal medicine. It aims to enhance comprehension, ensure terminological consistency, and support clear communication within academic, clinical, and translational settings.

The Glossary

No.	English term	Definition	Arabic Equivalent	Definition	Source
1	Ascariasis	an illness in people and animals caused by small worms that get inside the intestines. Example: The child was diagnosed with ascariasis after the doctor found roundworms in his stool sample.	داء الاسكارس	هو عدوى يُسببها الصفر الخراطيني، وهو دودة مدورة (ممسوده) معوية، أو في بعض الأحيان الصفر /الخنزيري، وهو دودة مدورة تسبب داء الأسكاريس عند الخنازير أيضًا	Cambridge Dictionary ,2025
2	Barrett's Esophagus	A condition in which the lining of your esophagus changes. The tissue that lines your esophagus becomes more like the tissue that lines your intestine. Example: The doctor diagnosed the patient with Barrett's esophagus after years of untreated acid reflux.	مريء باريت	إصْطِرَابٌ فِي الْمَرِيءِ السُّفْلِيِّ، يَتَمَيَّزُ بِأَقْطَعِ حَمِيْدَةٍ شَبِيْهِةٍ بِالْقَرْحَةِ فِي الْبَطْنَةِ ذَاتِ النَسِيْجِ الظَّهَارِيِّ الْعَمُوْدِيِّ، مِمَّا يُؤَدِّي فِي مُعْظَمِ الْأَحْيَانِ إِلَى تَهْيِيجٍ مُزْمِنٍ فِي الْمَرِيءِ بِفِعْلِ رَجُوعِ مَفْرَزَاتِ الْمَعِدَةِ وَالْغَضَارَاتِ الْهَضْمِيَّةِ الْحَمْضِيَّةِ إِلَيْهِ. وَتُعَدُّ هَذِهِ الْأَقْطَعُ قَابِلَةً لِلتَّحْوَلِ إِلَى وِرمِ خَبِيْثٍ	National Institutes of Health (NIH), 2025
3	Celiac Disease	Celiac disease is a chronic digestive and immune disorder that damages the small intestine. The disease is triggered by eating foods containing gluten. The disease can cause long-lasting digestive problems and keep your body from getting all the nutrients it needs.	الداء البطني	مرض مناعي ذاتي يتفاعل فيه جهاز المناعة مع الغلوتين، ما قد يؤدي أحيانًا إلى إلحاق الضرر بالأمعاء الدقيقة.	National Institutes of Health (NIH), 2025
4	Chronic gastritis	Is the chronic inflammation of gastric mucosa associated with varying degrees of damage of superficial and glandular epithelia. The causes of CG are exogenous (mainly Helicobacter pylori) and endogenous.	التهاب المعدة المزمن	هو حالة مزمنة تُصاب فيها الطبقة المخاطية المبطنة للمعدة، والمعروفة أيضًا بالغشاء المخاطي للمعدة، بالالتهاب أو التهيج لفترة طويلة. تميل الأعراض إلى الظهور ببطء مع مرور الوقت	Cheli et al., 1995

5	Colitis	An illness of the colon (= part of the bowels) in which the contents of the bowels are passed out of the body too often. Colitis can cause symptoms such as abdominal pain, diarrhea, and sometimes bleeding.	التهاب القولون	إصابة العشاء المخاطي للقولون بالالتهاب بعامل جرثومي، أو في بسبب أمراض المناعة الذاتية، أو بسبب تلوث المعالجات الكيميائية	Cambridge Dictionary, 2025
6	Colon cancer	Cancer that forms in the tissues of the colon (the longest part of the large intestine). Most colon cancers are adenocarcinomas (cancers that begin in cells that make and release mucus and other fluids). Example: A patient was diagnosed with colon cancer after routine screening detected a malignant adenoma in the descending colon.	سرطان القولون	سرطان القولون هو ورم سرطاني يصيب الأمعاء الغليظة المعروفة بالقولون والمستقيم وتزيد فرص الإصابة به بين الأشخاص بعد سن الخمسين من العمر	National Institutes of Health (NIH), 2025
7	Colonic fistula	A colonic fistula is an uncommon condition in which an abnormal connection forms between the colon and either the external body surface or another internal organ. It most often results from complications such as diverticular disease, Crohn's disease, malignancy, or surgical procedures. The patient developed a colonic fistula after surgery due to Crohn's disease.	ناسور قولوني	هو قناة غير طبيعية تتكون بين القولون وأحد الأعضاء المجاورة أو بين القولون وسطح الجسم الخارجي. تنشأ هذه الحالة عادة نتيجة التهابات مزمنة أو مضاعفات بعد العمليات الجراحية، كما قد ترتبط بأمراض مثل داء الرئوج أو داء كرون أو الأورام في الجهاز الهضمي.	Lavery, 1996
8	Crohn's disease	chronic inflammation that typically involves the lower portion of the ileum, often spreads to the colon, and is characterized by diarrhea, cramping, loss of appetite and weight, and the development of abscesses and scarring. The symptoms of Crohn's disease can be debilitating and	داء كرون	هو التهاب مزمن وغير مُعدٍ، يسبب التهاب وتهيج بطانة الجهاز الهضمي (من الفم إلى فتحة الشرج).	Merriam-Webster ,2025

		life-altering and can absolutely cause depression and isolation.			
9	Duodenitis	Inflammation of the duodenum (the first part of the small intestine that connects to the stomach). It causes symptoms such as upper abdominal pain, nausea, and bloating.	التهاب الاثنا عشر	التهاب يصيب الاثني عشر، وهو الجزء الأول من الأمعاء الدقيقة، ويقع أسفل المعدة مباشرة	National Institutes of Health (NIH), 2025
10	Dyspepsia	Inability to digest or difficulty in digesting something. Dyspepsia causes stomach pain and bloating after meals	عسر الهضم	قصور أو اضطراب في الوظيفة الهضمية يؤدي للإحساس بالانزعاج في البطن ولا سيما فوق السرة بعد تناول الطعام بفترة قصيرة.	Merriam-Webster, 2025
11	Enterocolitis	an illness that causes the colon (= the lower part of the bowels) and small intestine (= the upper part of the bowels) to become swollen and painful. In some cases, this is accompanied by blood in stools, which may be a symptom of enterocolitis.	التهاب معوي قولوني	إصابة جميع أقسام الأمعاء الدقيقة والقولونات الصاعدة والمستعرضة والنازلة والسيني والأعور بالتهاب.	Cambridge Dictionary, 2025
12	Enteritis	Inflammation of the intestines and especially of the human ileum. Example, The doctor diagnosed the patient with enteritis after several days of severe abdominal pain and diarrhea.	التهاب الأمعاء	إصابة الأمعاء بالتهاب، وبشكل خاص الأمعاء الدقيقة. ويحدث عادة بسبب تناول طعام أو شراب ملوث بميكروبات ممرضة، مثل السيراتيا، ولكن قد يكون له أسباب أخرى	Merriam-Webster, 2025
13	Epidemic viral gastroenteritis	Acute inflammation of the stomach and intestines caused by viruses such as rotaviruses and Norovirus-like agents. Outbreaks can lead to hundreds of diarrhea cases among children in a community.	التهاب المعدة والأمعاء الفيروسي الوبائي	التهاب المعدة والأمعاء الفيروسي. التهاب حاد وشديد العدوى، يعتقد أن سببه فيروسات مختلفة، يتظاهر بالإسهال والغثيان والإقياء مع	Estes & Graham, 1979
14	Esophagitis	An inflammation of the esophagus. It can make swallowing painful and difficult. Example: The patient's chest pain was caused by esophagitis resulting from chronic acid reflux.	التهاب المريء	لتهاب المريء. إصابة الغشاء المخاطي المبطن للمريء بالتهاب، قد يكون بسبب كيميائي أو بسبب جرثومي أو فطري.	Merriam-Webster, 2025

15	Functional dyspepsia	It is the medical term for a condition that causes upset, pain or discomfort in the stomach or upper abdomen. It is a common condition that may occur at any age, and it is accompanied by a feeling of satiety and fullness before finishing a meal.	عُسْرُ الهَضْمِ الوَطْنِيِّ	اضطراب مزمن في المعدة تظهر بسببه أعراض ألم المعدة، أو الحرق، أو الامتلاء، أو الانتفاخ، أو عدم القدرة على تناول وجبة طعام عادية.	Ministry of Health, Saudi Arabia (2025)
16	Gastroenteritis	An illness that causes the stomach and bowels to become swollen and painful. Example: Gastroenteritis often leads to vomiting and diarrhea, especially in children.	الْتِهَابُ المَعْدَةِ والْأَمْعَاءِ	إصابة كل من المعدة والأمعاء بالتهاب بسبب عامل معد (فيروس، أو جرثوم، أو فطر، أو حيوان أولي، أو طفيلي)، أو بسبب عوامل فيزيائية (الأشعة)، أو بسبب عوامل كيميائية أو مسببة للأرجية.	Cambridge Dictionary (2025);
17	Gastroesophageal reflux	It is a common condition that occurs due to the return of stomach acid and its contents to the esophagus, which many suffer from, including pregnant women from time to time, as it causes burning pain behind the sternum (burning), but its frequency and severity may be a problem that requires medical treatment.	مرض الارتجاع من المعدة إلى المريء	ألم متكرر في فؤاد المعدة وأسفل الصدر سببه عودة المفرزات من المعدة إلى المريء عبر الفوهة المرئية المعدية.	Ministry of Health, Saudi Arabia (2025)
18	Gastroesophageal varices	dilated submucosal distal esophageal veins connecting the portal and systemic circulations. They form due to portal hypertension, which commonly is a result of cirrhosis, resistance to portal blood flow, and increased portal venous blood inflow. Example: The patient with liver cirrhosis developed gastroesophageal varices, which caused severe bleeding.	دوالي المريء	هي أوردة متورمة في بطانة المريء. لا يمكنك رؤيتها أو الشعور بها، ولكن من المهم معرفة وجودها لأنها تُشكل خطر تمزق ونزيف داخلي. تحدث عادةً مع أمراض الكبد.	Alshaya & Almadi (2025), StatPearls
19	Gastrointestinal stromal tumor	Gastrointestinal stromal tumors (GISTs) are the most common mesenchymal tumors of the gastrointestinal (GI) tract. They are defined here as KIT	ورم سدوي هضمي	ورم في النسيج السدوي في جدار الجهاز الهضمي	Miettinen & Lasota, 2001

		(CD117, stem cell factor receptor)-positive mesenchymal spindle cell or epithelioid neoplasms primary in the GI tract, omentum, and mesentery. Example: The biopsy confirmed a gastrointestinal stromal tumor located in the stomach wall.			
20	Gastrinoma	A tumor that often involves blood vessels, usually occurs in the pancreas or the wall of the duodenum, and produces excessive amounts of gastrin, which stimulates gastric-acid secretion and consequent formation of ulcers, especially in the duodenum and the jejunum. Example: Multiple peptic ulcers were found, and further tests revealed a gastrinoma in the pancreas.	وَرَمٌ غاستريني	ورم في خلايا الغدد الصماء بالبنكرياس أو الاثني عشر يؤدي إلى إفراز كميات مفرطة من هرمون الغاسترين، مما يسبب زيادة في إنتاج حمض المعدة. ينتج عن ذلك قرحات هضمية متكررة وصعبة العلاج.	Merriam-Webster, 2025
21	Gastritis	inflammation especially of the mucous membrane of the stomach, including infection (Helicobacter pylori), drugs (nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, alcohol). Example: The patient was treated for gastritis caused by Helicobacter pylori infection.	التهابُ المعدة	إصابة الغشاء المخاطي للمعدة بالالتهاب	Merriam-Webster, 2025
22	Gastroparesis	A medical condition in which the stomach does not empty properly because of a problem with nerve signals to the stomach, rather than blockage, gastroparesis causes vomiting (in contrast to regurgitation) of food, which is not being digested further, from the stomach. Example: Gastroparesis made it difficult	خَزَلُ المعدة	اضطراب في حركة المعدة يؤدي إلى تباطؤ أو توقف إفراغ الطعام إلى الأمعاء الدقيقة دون وجود انسداد ميكانيكي . تشمل الأعراض الغثيان، القيء، الانتفاخ، وفقدان الشهية.	Cambridge Dictionary (2025);

		for the patient to digest food properly.			
23	Giardiasis	a condition caused by a parasite in the intestines, usually after drinking unsafe water. Example: The traveler developed giardiasis after drinking untreated water from a stream.	داء الجيارديايات	هو عدوى في الأمعاء الدقيقة، تنجم عن طفيلي من الأولي يُدعى الجيارديّة. الأعراض الرئيسية هي تشنجات في البطن وإسهال.	Cambridge Dictionary (2025)
24	Helicobacter pylori	a type of bacteria connected with diseases of the digestive system. Many people carry Helicobacter pylori without symptoms, but in some cases, it can lead to ulcers or stomach cancer.	جرثومة المعدة	وهي بكتيريا حلزونية الشكل تستقر في بطانة المعدة وتُعد من أهم أسباب التهاب المعدة والقرحة الهضمية. تسببها العدوى عادة من خلال الطعام أو الماء الملوّثين، أو عبر التلامس المباشر بين الأشخاص.	Cambridge Dictionary (2025)
25	Hepatitis	inflammation of the liver. It is caused by a variety of infectious viruses and non-infectious agents, leading to a range of health problems, including severe liver damage and cancer, some of which can be fatal.	التهاب الكبد	إصابة نسيج الكبد بالالتهاب بسبب عاملٍ معدٍ مثل الفيروسات والجراثيم والأوالي أو مواد كيميائية سامة أو مؤرّجة.	Merriam-Webster, 2025
26	Hirschsprung's disease	Hirschsprung's disease is a congenital disorder characterized by the absence of nerve cells (enteric ganglia) in parts of the colon, leading to bowel obstruction in newborns. Example: Babies with Hirschsprung's disease often have difficulty passing stool shortly after birth	داء هيرشسبرونغ	يُعرّف داء هيرشسبرونغ بأنه غياب الخلايا العصبية في أجزاء من الأمعاء الغليظة، مما يؤدي إلى صعوبة في إخراج البراز وحدث انسداد معوي لدى المواليد.	Kenny, Tam, & Garcia-Barcelo, 2010
27	Ileus	a condition in which food and waste cannot be moved through the intestine, causing it to be blocked. Example: After abdominal surgery, the patient developed ileus and required temporary bowel rest.	علوص شللي	حالة سريرية تنتج عن انسداد في الأمعاء وما يؤدي إليه من آلام ماغصة وتوقف خروج المواد البرازية والغازات.	Cambridge Dictionary (2025)

28	Irritable bowel syndrome(IBS)	It is a common chronic health condition that affects the large intestine (colon), causing abdominal cramps and flatulence (gaseous distention) Stress and certain foods can trigger symptoms of irritable bowel syndrome.	متلازمة التهيُّج في الأمعاء	مجموعة من الأعراض والعلامات تنتج من إصابة الأمعاء بأسباب تهيجية، تسبب تقلصات انتفاخ البطن	Ministry of Health, Saudi Arabia (2025)
29	Malabsorption syndrome	a syndrome resulting from malabsorption that is typically characterized by weakness, diarrhea, muscle cramps, edema, and loss of weight. Example: The patient with malabsorption syndrome loses weight and develops vitamin deficiencies due to poor nutrient absorption.	متلازمة سوء الامتصاص	اضطرابات في الامتصاص المعوي للمغذيات، يتميز بنقص الشهية، وفقد الوزن، وانتفاخ البطن، ومغص عضلي، وآلم عظمي، وإسهال دهني. ويحدث فقر الدم، والوهن، والتعب نتيجة عدم امتصاص الحديد، وحمض الفوليك، وفيتامين ب 12 بكميات كافية.	Merriam-Webster, 2025
30	Malabsorption	faulty absorption especially of nutrient materials from the gastrointestinal tract. Malabsorption can lead to fatigue and anemia because the body fails to absorb essential nutrients.	سوء الامتصاص	خلل يصيب امتصاص المواد الغذائية من الأمعاء. قد يكون مقتصرًا على عنصر واحد مثل اللاكتوز أو فئة غذائية معينة كالبروتينات، وقد يكون سببه عوز بعض الإنزيمات الهضمية أو سبب ميكانيكي (تلو العمليات الجراحية) أو بسبب التهابات مزمنة.	Merriam-Webster, 2025
31	Necrotizing enterocolitis	is a life-threatening illness almost exclusively affecting neonates with a mortality rate as high as 50 percent. The pathophysiology of NEC is inflammation of the intestine leading to bacterial invasion causing cellular damage and cellular death and necrosis of the colon and intestine.	التهاب معوي قولوني ناجر	هو موت أنسجة الأمعاء. يصيب هذا المرض بشكل رئيسي الأطفال الخدج أو حديثي الولادة المرضى، ويحدث عندما تموت بطانة جدار الأمعاء وتتساقط أنسجتها.	National Institutes of Health (NIH), 2025
32	Pancreatitis	Pancreatitis is inflammation of the pancreas. Acute pancreatitis is short term and may go away in a few days with treatment. Chronic, or long-lasting,	التهاب البنكرياس	التهاب يصيب البنكرياس ويؤدي إلى ألم في البطن، غثيان، قيء، وارتفاع إنزيمات البنكرياس. قد يكون حادًا أو مزمنًا.	National Institutes of Health (NIH), 2025

		pancreatitis can get worse over time and cause lasting damage.			
33	Peptic ulcer	a painful sore inside the stomach or another part of the digestive system. Peptic ulcers are often caused by Helicobacter pylori infection or long-term use of painkillers.	الْقَرْحَةُ الهَضْمِيَّة	تقرحات تصيب المعدة وغالباً ما تكون من زيادة في الحموضة	Merriam-Webster, 2025
34	Stress ulcer	An ulcer in the esophagus, stomach, or upper small intestine caused by excess acid produced as a result of physical stress, such as surgery, major burns, head injury, or other trauma. Critically ill patients in intensive care may develop stress ulcers due to severe physical stress or trauma.	قَرْحَةُ الْكَرْبِ	قَرْحَةُ هَضْمِيَّة، غالباً ما تكون في المعدة، تنتج عن الإصابة بالكرب.	Stanford Children's Health, n. d
35	Tropical sprue	a condition where food is not absorbed into the body, causing diarrhea. People living in tropical areas may develop tropical sprue due to chronic intestinal infections.	دَرْبٌ مَدَارِيٌّ	حالة من سوء الامتصاص تكثر في المناطق المدارية بسبب ذيفان معوي تفرزه بعض الجراثيم يؤدي لاضطراب امتصاص الدسم والكسيلوز والفيتامين B12	Cambridge Dictionary (2025)
36	ulcerative colitis	It is a chronic disease, which affects the innermost lining of the large intestine often (the lower part of the colon and rectum), causing inflammation or swelling and ulcers called ulcers on the innermost lining of the large intestine and resulting in diarrhea and bleeding.	الْتِهَابُ الْقَوْلُونِ التَّقْرِجِيُّ	التهاب القولون التقرحي. مرض التهابي يصيب غشاء القولون المخاطي، والطبقة تحت المخاطية، يتميز سريريا بالألم معوية ومستقيمية.	Ministry of Health, Saudi Arabia (2025)
37	Viral Gastroenteritis	An infection of your intestines that typically causes watery diarrhea, pain or cramping in your abdomen, nausea or vomiting, and sometimes fever. People commonly call viral gastroenteritis "stomach flu," but the term is not medically correct. Flu viruses do not cause viral gastroenteritis.	الْتِهَابُ الْمَعِدَةِ وَالْأَمْعَاءِ الْفَيْرُوسِيَّ	لتهاب في الأمعاء يسببه فيروس. وتشتمل أعراضه عادةً على مغص في البطن، وإسهال، وغثيان، وقيء.	National Institutes of Health (NIH), 2025

38	Viral Hepatitis	Viral hepatitis is an infection that causes liver inflammation and damage. Several different viruses cause hepatitis, including hepatitis A, B, C, D, and E. The hepatitis A and E viruses typically cause acute infections.	التهاب الكبد الفيروسي	التهاب الكبد الفيروسي. أحد أشكال التهاب الكبد، سببه فيروس، قد يكون من النوع المصلي B، وقد يكون من النوع A.	Ministry of Health, Saudi Arabia, 2025
39	Volvulus	a twisting of the intestine upon itself that causes obstruction. Emergency surgery is often required when a volvulus causes intestinal obstruction.	انفتال الأمعاء	التواء الأمعاء على نفسها مما يسبب انسداداً معويًا. وأكثر ما تحدث في الجزء الأخير من الأمعاء الدقيقة (اللفائفي) أو الأعور أو الأجزاء السينية من القولون.	Merriam-Webster, 2025
40	Yersiniosis	is typically an enteric disease in chinchillas and signs may include diarrhea, weight loss, anorexia, severe abdominal pain, dehydration, and bloody feces. Yersiniosis can spread through eating undercooked pork or contaminated milk.	داء اليرسينيات	هو مرض معد تسببه بكتيريا من جنس يرسينيا تعيش في أمعاء الحيوانات والبشر. وتتجلى أعراض هذا المرض في الإصابة بالأم في البطن والحمى.	, The Laboratory Rabbit, Guinea Pig, Hamster, and Other Rodents

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